

Original Research Article: A Comparison of the Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV) of Patients with Stable COPD and Those with Acute Exacerbation (AECOPD)

Ravi Gaur¹, Ritumbhara², Ved Praksh Meghwal³, Mohit Gaur⁴

¹Assistant Professor, Department of General Medicine, J L N Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

²Senior Resident, Department of Respiratory Medicine, J L N Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

³Senior Resident, Department of General Medicine, Sardar Patel medical College, Bikaner, Rajasthan, India

⁴Junior Resident, Department of Medicine, J L N Medical College, Ajmer, Rajasthan, India

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Corresponding Author: Dr. Ravi Gaur

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Abstract:

Background: Chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) is the third leading cause of death worldwide, and it represents a major health, social and economic burden. Macrocytosis (MCV>94 fl) is frequently observed at patients suffering from chronic obstructive pulmonary disease (COPD) with or without respiratory insufficiency.

Objectives: The objectives of the study is to Compare Mean Corpuscular volume (MCV) between Acute Exacerbation and stable COPD patients.

Methodology: This Hospital based case control study includes 50 patients with primary and final diagnosis of AECOPD. 50 subjects in stable period of COPD. A random Blood sample was collected from all subjects and analysed for MCV, WBC, RDW and MPV on the same day within 3 hours of collection. Data was recorded as per Performa. The data analysis was done. For categoric variables chi-square test was used. For continuous variables independent samples t-test was used. P-value <0.05 was considered as significant.

Results: Maximum patients in both groups were found in >60 yrs age group. The mean age in AECOPD group was 64.62±8.24 yrs and in Stable COPD was 63.22±9.18 yrs. Maximum patients in both groups were from middle class followed by lower socio-economic class. BMI was significantly lower in AECOPD patients (20.94±2.15 kg/mt²) as compare to stable COPD patients (21.37±3.10kg/mt²). Maximum patients in both groups were having cough and breathlessness. Maximum patients in both groups were smoker. 58.00% patients in AECOPD and 30.00% patients in stable COPD group were present smoker. Maximum patients in AECOPD group were from GOLD stage 4 and in stable COPD were also from GOLD stage 4. Mean FEV1 % was significantly lower in AECOPD patients (43.87±14.26) as compare to stable COPD patients (48.12±20.18). The difference in both groups was found statistically significant. MCV was significantly lower in AECOPD (82.04±1.49) as compare to stable COPD patients (86.50±1.87). The difference in both groups was found statistically significant 4.00% hospital mortality in AECOPD group.

Conclusion: The current study's results indicate that there was a statistically significant correlation between the MCV and the mortality rate, length of hospital stay, and severity of COPD. Furthermore, it was shown that there was a substantial correlation between the severity of COPD and patient mortality, meaning that the majority of study mortality involved individuals with severe COPD.

Keywords: AECOPD, MCV, FEV, RDW.

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Introduction

COPD has been among the top eight leading causes of disabilities in all the states. Comprising all these, DALYs due to COPD increased 36.3% from 1990 to 2016 and it became second leading cause of DALYs in India followed by diarrheal disease, lower respiratory tract infections, stroke and iron deficiency anemia. The prevalence of COPD has increased by 29.2% within the same period which

is a serious public health concern. [1] The GOLD defines an exacerbation COPD as “an event characterized by dyspnea and/or cough and sputum that worsen over ≤14 days, which may be accompanied by tachypnea and/or tachycardia and is often associated with increased local and systemic inflammation caused by airway infection, pollution, or other insult to the airways” [2]. Causes

of exacerbation of COPD are multiple and include infections, heart failure, pulmonary embolism, and gastroesophageal reflux [3,4,5,6]; of these causes, infections are the most common [7]. These infective episodes may be due to bacterial, viral, and, rarely, fungal infections [8]. Quantification of the severity exacerbations in COPD is usually made clinically and is based on the symptoms, physical signs, and response to therapy. Pulmonary function tests (PFTs) have no role in assessing the severity of COPD exacerbation, although they are the cornerstone of the diagnostic evaluation of patients with suspected COPD [2,9,10], and at present, there is no method for quantifying the severity of COPD exacerbations.

Our aim was to investigate the relationship of different CBC parameters such as hemoglobin level, MCV or RDW with COPD exacerbation severity.

Material and Methods

This Hospital based case control study was conducted at Department of General Medicine, S.P. Medical College and A.G of Hospital, Bikaner, Rajasthan from 1 august 2019 to 31 July 2020

We have included hospitalized 50 patients with primary and final diagnosis of AECOPD. 50 subjects in stable period of COPD.

Inclusion Criteria: Diagnosed case of COPD with clinical criteria's of exacerbation including increased dyspnea, increased sputum volume or sputum purulence, cough. Age group above 30 yrs age. Those who are giving informed consent.

Exclusion Criteria: A primary reason for admission other than AECOPD. Any hematological disease, oncologic disease. Any auto-immune disease. Any history of systemic illness like diabetes, hypertension on medication. Not given informed consent.

A random Blood sample was collected from the antecubital vein of the study subjects. The blood samples were analysed on the same day within 3 hours of collection. The biochemical parameters relevant to the study were analysed by the following methodologies.

With Differential Test Method

Table 1: Socio-economic status wise distribution of study subject

Socioeconomic status	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
Upper	0	0	0.99
Middle	32	31	
Lower	18	19	

Table no 1 shows that maximum patients in both groups were from middle class followed by lower socio-economic class. Both groups were comparable.

WBC: Flow cytometry, RBC: Impedance counting, Platelet Count: Impedance counting, Hb: Converted to SLS-hemoglobin and read photometrically.

MCV: The average volume of individual erythrocytes derived from the RBC histogram.

RDW: The size distribution spread of the erythrocytes population derived from the RB Histogram.

MPV: The average volume of individual platelets derived from the PLT histogram.

Mean Corpuscular Volume (MCV)

A mean corpuscular volume (MCV) is a type of blood test that measures the size of your red blood cells. It is included in a routine panel of tests called a complete blood count (CBC). For adults, MCV levels normally fall between 80 and 100 femtoliters (fl). The MCV test is not used alone but interpreted along with other tests in the CBC. When interpreted as such, the MCV test can be useful for:

- Diagnosing anemia (a disorder that reduces the ability of red blood cells to carry oxygen to tissues)
- Determining the causes of anemia based on whether your red blood cells are small (microcytic), large (macrocytic), or normal (normocytic anemia).

Data Analysis:

Data was recorded as per Performa. The data analysis was done. For categoric variables chi-square test was used. For continuous variables independent samples t-test was used. P-value <0.05 was considered as significant.

Results

This was a hospital-based case-control study in the age group of above 30 years in hospitalized 50 patients with a primary and definite diagnosis of acute exacerbation of COPD and 50 participants in stable period of COPD conducted among admitted to the department of medicine. The mean age in AECOPD group was 64.62±8.24 yrs and in Stable COPD was 63.22±9.18 yrs. Maximum patients in both groups were male.

Table 2: BMI wise distribution of study subject

BMI in kg/mt ²	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
Mean	20.94±2.15	21.37±3.10	0.01

Table no 2 shows that mean BMI was significantly lower in AECOPD patients (20.94±2.15 kg/mt²) as compare to stable COPD patients (21.37±3.10kg/mt²)

Table 3: Symptoms wise Distribution of study subject

Symptoms	AECOPD	Stable COPD
Breathlessness	50	23
Expectoration	30	20
Cough	35	32
Wheezing	9	8
Chest pain	15	9

Table no 3 shows that maximum patients in both groups were presented with cough and breathlessness.

Table 4: Smoking status wise distribution of study subject

Smoking	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
Smoker	29	15	0.01
Ex-smoker	16	30	
No smoker	5	5	

Table no 4 shows that maximum patients in both groups were smoker. 58.00% patients in AECOPD and in 30.00% patients in stable COPD group were present smoker. The difference in both group was found statically significant.

Table 5: GOLD criteria wise distribution of study subject

GOLD stage	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
A	7	13	0.006
B	3	8	
C	14	8	
D	26	21	

Table no 9 shows that maximum patients in AECOPD group was from GOLD stage 4 and in stable COPD was also from GOLD stage 4. The difference in both group was found statically significant.

Table 6: FEV1 wise distribution of study subject

FEV1%	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
Mean± SD	43.87±14.26	48.12±20.18	0.001

Table no 6 shows that mean FEV1% significantly lower in AECOPD patients (43.87±14.26) as compare to stable COPD patients (48.12±20.18). The difference in both groups was found statistically significant.

Table 7: Outcome wise distribution of study subject

Outcome	AECOPD	Stable COPD
Death	2	0
Survived	48	50

Table no 7 shows that 4.00% hospital mortality in AECOPD group.

Table 8: MCV wise distribution of study subject

MCV(fl)	AECOPD	Stable COPD	p-value
Mean± SD	82.04±1.49	86.50±1.87	0.001

Graph 1: Showing Comparison of MCV between two Groups

Table no 8 shows that mean MCV was significantly lower in AECOPD (82.04 ± 1.49 fl) as compare to stable patients (86.50 ± 1.87 fl). The difference in both groups was found statistically significant

Discussion

AECOPD is among the most common diseases in clinical practice, especially in patients with infections. Inflammation encompasses a complex network of interactions involving various immune-related cells, including neutrophils and lymphocytes, which can lead to persistent respiratory tissue injury and damage.[11] It has been reported that the absolute counts of key immune-related cell populations in the peripheral blood and their ratios, can adequately reflect chronic inflammatory conditions[12]

In our study maximum patients in both groups were found in >60 yrs age group. The mean age in AECOPD group was 64.62 ± 8.24 yrs and in Stable COPD was 63.22 ± 9.18 yrs. Maximum patients in both groups were male. Angus et al., [13] observed that the mean age of patients with AECOPD was 63.8 years. In another study conducted by Martin et al, there was an increased incidence of sepsis by about 20 % more in the elderly population compared to younger individuals [14].

The reason for this high incidence among elderly population may be due to the fact that, in recent years life expectancy has increased in general and that with increasing age, individuals develop various co-morbidities like diabetes and malignancy which increase the risk of developing sepsis. We could not come to a conclusion based on gender incidence as our study group was small and as there was not much significant difference in male and female incidence. Our study was compatible with Ercan Kurtipek et al[15] who reported that out of the 94 patients, 48(51%) had stable COPD with a mean age of 66.65 ± 10.17 years

(range: 49-79 years) and 46(49%) patients having acute exacerbation with a mean age of 62.67 ± 9.41 years (range: 48-92 years). Another study by Recai Ergün et al [16] reported the mean age of the patients as 69.0 ± 9.2 and 104 (78.2%) of patients were male.

In our study maximum patients in both groups were from middle class followed by lower socio-economic class because our hospital was government sector hospital, so maximum patients in our hospital come from lower and middle socio-economic class. BMI was significantly lower in AECOPD patients (20.94 ± 2.15 kg/mt²) as compare to stable COPD patients (21.37 ± 3.10 kg/mt²). The loss of weight is most likely multifactorial in origin. Established explanations for weight loss in COPD include increased basal metabolic rate due to the increased energy cost of breathing, as well as physical inactivity and malnutrition due to eating difficulties.

Systemic inflammation and hypoxia are particularly prevalent among COPD patients with low body weight. [17] There is increasing evidence that the immune system, in particular inflammatory cytokines, play an important role in the development of weight loss and cachexia. The central cytokine in the loss of muscle mass is TNF- α . TNF- α , which in laboratory animals is associated with accelerated metabolism and protein turnover, was shown to be elevated in the blood of COPD patients suffering from involuntary weight loss.[18,19]The present study observed that maximum patients in both groups were smoker. 58.00% patients in AECOPD and in 30.00% patients in stable COPD group were present smoker. The difference in both groups was found statistically significant. Fletcher et al [20] revealed that in susceptible smokers (comparable with the host factors), tobacco smoking is strongly related to chronic bronchitis and airflow obstruction and that

these were two different diseases. Cigarette smoking is recognized as the cause of COPD in the vast majority of patients. Although not fully understood, it is widely accepted that an abnormal inflammatory response of the lungs to noxious particles and gases beyond the normal protective inflammatory response is involved in the development of COPD.

In our study maximum patients in AECOPD groups were from GOLD stage 4 and in stable COPD were also from GOLD stage 4. The difference in both group was found statistically significant. Our results were supported by a retrospective study done by TAYLAN et al. [21] who reported that out of 100 patients, 43 cases were classified as Global Initiative for Chronic Obstructive Lung Disease (GOLD) III and 57 as GOLD IV. Ercan Kurtipek et al [15] who found that among the stable COPD patients, 16(33.3%) were in category B and 18(37.5%) in category D. Among AECOPD patients, 34(73.9%) were in category D, which was conflict of our results.

Furthermore, the mean MCV in this study decreased with the increasing of the hospital stay. Moreover, the mean MCV decreased and increased slightly with increasing of the severity of the disease, respectively. Kontoninas et al.[22]'s study revealed that MCV was directly and significantly related to the severity of COPD such that the mean MCV was much lower in patients with mild to moderate COPD as compared to AECOPD patients.

Conclusion

The current study's results indicate that there was a statistically significant correlation between the MCV and the mortality rate, length of hospital stay, and severity of COPD. Furthermore, it was shown that there was a substantial correlation between the severity of COPD and patient mortality, meaning that the majority of study mortality involved individuals with severe COPD.

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